

UK development assistance in health in Ghana: A 30 - year perspective

Abstract

Motivation

We seek to redress the paucity of publications on reflective learning in the context of international development assistance by exploring support to a country (and a specific sector) over a significant time frame. This case study is therefore uniquely positioned to advance good development policy making.

Purpose

This paper covers 1993 to 2023. It links the story of UK support to the evolution of Ghana's health sector.

Approach and methods

We interviewed over 30 informants and reviewed documents about UK development policies and programmes, the Ghanaian health sector and aid effectiveness. Moreover, we reviewed unpublished reports from DFID and later FCDO.

Six phases are identified. Each phase presents key developments in Ghana's health sector, the nature of UK support and wider UK international development policy.

Findings

The learning, in the main, pertains to SWAp (Sector Wide Approach) programmes – the major development approach of this 30-year period, championed globally by the Ghana and UK governments. Our exploration of Ghana's health SWAps revealed, first, how political ideology and changing policy emphases influenced the UK's approach in Ghana. Second, and related to political influences, we note the cyclical nature of history, with discussions about aid effectiveness in Ghana in 2023 having distinct echoes of the debates of the late 1990s.

Policy Implications

Whilst the scale of development assistance and the modalities of today differ from those of the recent past, the principles of a SWAp endure in today's discourse in Ghana. SWAps, with their focus on agreed priorities, have impact but are hard to sustain, not least because what constitutes 'good enough' government systems and the expected pace of reform are subjective judgements. This case study is an example of how reflecting on past experiences is of value to enriching the evolution of development policy.

Introduction

This paper describes the UK's investment in Ghana's health sector from 1993 to 2023. It addresses the paucity of publications about UK development assistance to a country over a significant period of time and explores influences on the form and scale of assistance. It links the story of UK support to developments in Ghana at the time and explores the influence of wider UK development policy.

Six phases are identified, delineated by the UK's main bilateral health support programmes. For each phase, the paper looks at key developments in Ghana's health sector, the nature of UK support, and what was happening in terms of wider UK policy in international development. The focus on UK policy is included because development assistance is, by its very nature, political, with one country's politics affecting what happens in another.

This paper describes Ghana's evolution from low-income status (when large-scale health systems strengthening projects and support for service delivery were appropriate) to lower-middle income status and the decline in development assistance budgets. An important feature of the period 1998-2015 was the existence of a SWAp (Sector Wide Approach), which this paper discusses at length because Ghana and the UK were both global leaders in this partnership approach. Some development approaches and tools are elaborated on in Annex 1.

We show how changes in UK politics affected development assistance in Ghana. Political ideology and the resulting changing policy emphases (such as results measurement or risk tolerance) influenced the UK's approach. We note the cyclical nature of history, with discussions about aid effectiveness in 2023 having distinct echoes of the debates of the late 1990s. The paper ends with a discussion of what has been learnt.

Key findings: Overview of the six phases

The paper focuses on DFID's (later FCDO's) main programmes: large-value health systems and policy development programmes which supported jointly agreed five-year Programmes of Work (POW) of Ghana's Ministry of Health (MoH). The main modality was Financial Aid (FA) in varying forms, plus Technical Assistance (see Annex 1). The UK also supported smaller topic-specific projects (total values shown in Figure 2). Although not discussed here given the paper's focus, these projects complemented the large health programmes well, especially through sharing financial and operational risks during significant and challenging system changes (e.g. new health insurance reimbursement mechanisms) or piloting a new strategy (e.g. malaria chemoprophylaxis for under-5s).

In summary, the story starts in 1993 with an innovative Health Sector Aid Programme (HSAP). Later the UK contributed to a MoH-managed Pooled Health Fund as part of a SWAp. This developed in 2008 into a combination of Sector Budget Support (SBS) and General Budget Support (GBS). SBS was channelled through the Ministry of Finance and managed completely by the Government of Ghana (allocation, reporting

and auditing). This modality ended in 2014 and was replaced with earmarked FA to specific programmes, with DFID heavily involved in the details of design and implementation. After 2020, UK support declined considerably in financial terms, shifting towards directly awarded contracts to implement projects, and social sector rather than health-specific programmes. During long periods, DFID (later FCDO) chaired the development partners' (DPs) health group, thus leading DP engagement with the MoH.

Over the 30-year period the UK consistently focused support on sector governance and equity. Governance included sustained engagement on health financing, public financial management, sector planning and monitoring, and (latterly) regulatory capacity and accountability. An equity focus was adopted through capacity development for national health insurance, the Ghana Health Service, community health and mental health. A sustained governance and equity perspective allowed the UK to contribute to the efficiency, effectiveness and accountability of the Ghanaian health system.

Figure 1 illustrates the six phases, whilst Figure 2 shows UK spending by phase. Spending is broken down to show the main health sector programme, the health component of GBS, and other bilateral health projects. In Phase 1 the majority of spending was on the main health systems support programme rather than smaller projects — the reverse was true in Phase 6. GBS was extremely important in Phase 4 (2007-2012), of minor importance in Phases 3 and 5, and otherwise non-existent. All the figures are estimates; Phase 6 figures represent overall social sector support, as the spend specifically on health could not be determined.

Figure 1: The 6 phases of support and key events

Figure 2: DFID/FCDO spending in health in Ghana, (1993-2023¹)

Source: Dev tracker, FCDO official estimates, and project reports

Phase One (1993 - 1997): Emerging interest in a SWAp

Core UK Programme: Health Sector Aid Programme (HSAP), 1993-1996

Value of Programme: ca £12 million

Ghana and the UK were both interested in more efficient partnership working and in health systems strengthening.

Ghana's health sector

At the start of the 1990s Ghana's government health sector was under-performing and cash starved. Infrastructure had deteriorated and there was little recurrent financing beyond salaries. There had been a significant exodus of health professionals and user fees had been introduced in the 1980s to tackle persistent drug shortages.

Benefiting from greater political and economic stability, as well as strong technical leadership, a national health system that focused on primary health care, with regional and district health management teams, slowly strengthened in the second half of the 1990s (Waddington & Enyimayew, 1989, 1990).

DPs became increasingly impressed by the MoH's capacity in strategic planning and operational management; international spending on health increased. DPs wanted to

¹ Phase 6 data is pro-rata for the two main social sector programmes that continued beyond 2023.

see strong health planning, but paradoxically the uncoordinated activities of multiple partners undermined central planning. Ghanaian officials realised that the preponderance of DPs brought new challenges: DPs focused on specific parts of the system which resulted in resource allocation distortion; there was limited capacity building; many relatively small-scale projects were never scaled up; and a fragmented approach led to gaps and duplications that did not necessarily reflect national priorities.

By 1996 Ghana's government was addressing these challenges and was a global thought leader in the conceptualisation of the Sector Wide Approach (SWAp) – see Annex 1 **Error! Reference source not found.** The development of SWAps was largely a result of experience in Ghana and Zambia - countries whose leaders wanted 'to do business differently' (Cassels, 1997).

ODA in Ghana

From 1993 to 1996 the Overseas Development Administration's (ODA)² main programme was the Health Sector Aid Programme (HSAP). HSAP was unusual for its time because it was emphatically a health systems strengthening programme with results in terms of health impact initially assumed, but only roughly described. The philosophy was that well-functioning systems were a necessary part of the MoH's effectiveness. Resources were provided through FA and managed jointly by the MoH and ODA, while HSAP also funded TA and the procurement of equipment and vehicles.

The first logical framework for ODA's HSAP was devised in 1996. By 1997 a list of 20 core indicators had been agreed by the MoH and several DPs. Whilst an important breakthrough in terms of streamlined shared monitoring, the list encountered many practical problems. For example, some indicators quickly had 100% achievement but were not adapted for some time.

UK international development policy

In 1997 New Labour came to power, with an international commitment to poverty reduction based on the principles of partnership and country ownership. UK national interest was not an overt consideration (Valters & Whitty, 1997). The prevailing discourse in Ghana during this phase - with its emphasis on national ownership, a holistic view of the sector and health systems strengthening – complemented the new UK policy direction. The UK became an early supporter and shaper of the SWAp concept.

As aid instruments evolved, so did ODA's internal management systems. In 1993 the financial management systems were not well-suited to supporting flexible local decision-making: email was not yet widely available, and funding requests were sent by fax or diplomatic bag. A manual imprest account was managed locally. Over time this system was streamlined with electronic transfers to pooled funds, and later to Ghana's treasury.

² The Overseas Development Administration, the predecessor to DFID, was part of the Foreign and Commonwealth Office.

Phase Two (1998 - 2001): The birth of the SWAp

Core UK Programme: Health Sector Improvement Programme I (HSIP I), 1998-2001

Value of Programme: ca £38.8 million

The building blocks of the SWAp are developed, with strong support from DFID.

Ghana's health sector

During 1997 and 1998 the MoH and DPs worked on a series of documents to operationalise a SWAp. The work reflected a significant shared commitment to strengthening institutions and systems related to planning, budgeting, financial management, procurement and human resources.

The first SWAp programme was based on three documents: the Medium-Term Health Strategy, the first Five-Year Programme of Work (POW-I) 1997-2001, and the Common Management Arrangements (CMA). The CMA, which covered planning, funding channels and monitoring, described how DPs could work together to support the Ministry's POW and reduce fragmentation and transaction costs.

POW-I reflected Ghana's commitment to improving the nation's health, with the following objectives:

- increasing geographical and financial access to basic services
- improving quality of healthcare
- improving efficiency
- fostering closer collaboration with communities and other sectors
- increasing resources in the sector and promoting equity.

POW-I heralded a new relationship between the MoH and DPs. Some DPs supported it through their own parallel projects and others through the Pooled Health Fund established in 1997. A Memorandum of Understanding was signed between the MoH and participating DPs. The funds were managed by the MoH, while a DP-approved audit firm conducted annual audits in conjunction with the national Public Audit Body. Initially the Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA) and DFID contributed to the Health Fund, with the EU, the Netherlands, and the World Bank joining in 1998 (Addai & Gaere, 2001; Ghana MoH, 1996).

The management arrangements were regarded as innovative because the MoH had considerable leeway to plan how resources were utilised within the programme's broad parameters. This was a clear change from the more specific project support of the past and began a long period when DFID and other DPs worked in this way (Asamoah-Baah & Smithson, 1999).

Financial management in the MoH had traditionally been highly centralised, with the result that district health offices had minimal access to cash, little financial management experience and were thus poorly able to respond flexibly to needs. In the mid-1990s District Budget Management Centres were created to accredit

districts as fit to manage funds. A systematic approach focused extensive support for districts and enabled the disbursement of substantial resources at local level.

The SWAp principles were operationalised. Twice-annual reviews were held: one to review progress – informed by independent review and audit – and the other to agree on the following year's coverage and policy targets. The POW-I review - Health of the Nation (Ghana MoH, 1997) - noted that while it attracted more DP funding, with more reaching districts, this had not translated into improved sector performance. Implementation of government reforms faced long delays, and local level plans lacked adequate scrutiny and monitoring. Nevertheless, the SWAp was influential and informed global thinking about aid effectiveness.

DFID in Ghana

DFID replaced ODA in 1997 and responded to POW-I with the Health Sector Improvement Programme (HSIP) of 1998-2001, with a value of around £38.8 million – a significant increase in funding from Phase 1. HSIP was aimed at increasing access to quality health services.

HSIP used two aid modalities. It provided FA through the Pooled Health Fund: DFID was deeply involved in the design of the Fund and shaped its evolution. It also engaged TA to support reforms and new policies, such as increased capacity of the decentralised Budget Management Centres, establishment of an internal audit unit in the MoH and launching the Ghana Health Service.

HSIP, the Health Fund, and the alignment of support with POW-I priorities demonstrated confidence in Ghana's national leadership and management systems. The targets of the national programme were adopted into DFID's monitoring and accountability tool, the logical framework (logframe).

UK international development policy

The prevailing UK development policy of Phase 1 continued – the 2000 White Paper described an increased focus on Africa, larger budgets and a firm MDG focus (Lowcock & Dissanayake, 2024). The UK saw itself as contributing to a country's progress through shared goals; specific attribution to DFID was not seen as important. Ideas were evolving about aid effectiveness and the importance of harmonised systems of support and alignment with national plans. Reflecting its support for SWAps, DFID published a guide for its health advisers - Developing Sector Wide Approaches in the Health Sector (Walford, 1998).

Phase Three (2002 - 2006): The SWAp evolves, silent partnership and general budget support

Core UK Programme: Health Sector Improvement Programme II (HSIP-II), 2002-2006

Value of Programme: ca £40 million

A mature SWAp, including DFID as a silent partner, is complemented by GBS.

Ghana's health sector

Ghana's Programme of Work from 2002-2006 (POW-II) was called Partnerships for Health: Bridging the Inequalities Gap. It echoed the priorities of the Ghana Poverty Reduction Strategy that was developed as part of work in the so-called 'highly indebted poor countries' in 2002. POW-II had three objectives:

- bridging equity gaps in access to quality health services
- ensuring sustainable financing arrangements that protected the poor
- enhancing efficiency in service delivery.

In response to this strategic direction, the National Health Insurance Agency was created in 2005 (elevated to an Authority in 2012) with the aim of improving access to care for poorer people. There was major investment in primary health care through a programme called Community Health Planning and Services (CHPS).

POW-II contributed to good overall sector outcomes. However, progress on pro-poor initiatives and overall governance and performance was mixed. Little progress was made on the equitable distribution of personnel and the ratio of salary to non-salary expenditure. The roll-out of CHPS was sporadic and hampered by the low level of non-salary spending. Nonetheless, health sector wages rose, the migration of health workers abroad was curbed and user-fees at service delivery points were officially abolished.

POW-II was guided by an updated CMA (CMA-II). POW-II continued to mature the SWAp ways of working: twice yearly health summits, business meetings and annual independent assessments became important events. These activities provided opportunities for health, Ministry of Finance, local government officials and implementers to debate progress and challenges with DPs. The MoH and DPs had productive policy engagement and the fiduciary governance was considered good. There was strong international interest in the SWAp.

Beyond the health sector there were major changes in the way that Government and DPs worked together. In 2003 the Government signed agreements with a number of DPs to create the Multi-Donor Budget Support (MDBS) partnership – see Annex 1. Overall DFID contributed around £304.5 million through GBS, peaking in 2008 and significantly tailing off in 2011-2015.

The main reasons for starting GBS in 2003 were at the macro level, notably Parliamentary endorsement of the Poverty Reduction Strategy and International

Monetary Fund (IMF) approval for a new growth facility (Lawson et al., 2007). One suggested benefit of GBS was that it improved policy dialogue between government and DPs within sectors, though this was less evident in education and health, where SWAp had already promoted dialogue. Whilst GBS was judged in evaluations to have brought improvements in the national aid architecture, and Ghana's legal and policy framework, it encountered the same problems as SBS in failing to influence some long-running challenges, notably the very high percentage of the recurrent budget spent on wages (EU Commission et al., 2017). Moreover many MoH officials did not support GBS, fearing the health sector's traditionally high level of financial support from DPs might be eroded.

DFID in Ghana

DFID continued its involvement with the SWAp, supporting a national strategic health plan, adopting its results framework, engaging in SWAp processes, and providing a sizeable increase in funding including for TA.

As the SWAp evolved, there were two significant changes to DFID's support. First, there was a move away from the pooled Health Fund towards SBS, which was channelled through the Ministry of Finance, but earmarked for the MoH. This was using, and displaying confidence in, Ghana's administrative structure. SBS remained the leading modality for UK support until 2012.

Secondly, a period called the 'silent partnership' started in 2004 and lasted until 2010. DFID remained a major funder, but programme management was done through pooled arrangements. DFID delegated its 'seat at the policy table' to the Netherlands Embassy and did not have a resident adviser. However, DFID was not entirely 'silent', as it participated in some key missions and debates.

The silent partnership was devised when DFID increased its funding significantly and when the SWAp was regarded as performing well, but faced significant challenges following a less stable period of declining DP confidence in results. It ended in 2010 (Phase 4) because DFID started to increase its monitoring requirements and the Netherlands found the role increasingly onerous. This increased interest in results reflected a DFID-wide shift away from delegated responsibility.

The silent partnership period was in stark contrast to other times when DFID was often nominated as the lead DP amongst collaborators. It was promoted centrally by DFID when there was great enthusiasm for partnership working: adopting 'one voice' amongst DPs, encouraging government leadership and reducing transaction costs. It also saved UK management funds – an estimated £100,000 per year.

The silent partnership arrangement was not always understood by other partners, many of whom (including key MoH staff) were left believing that DFID had 'lost interest' in the Ghanaian health sector (Walford, 2007b).

UK international development policy

By 2005 there was cross-party consensus aligning with the Labour government's development approach, and their political commitment to provide 0.7% of Gross National Income as aid spending by 2013.

The UK was a major proponent of the 2005 Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness that sought to institutionalise co-ordination through the principles of harmonisation and alignment. The UK's international development policy fitted well with Ghana's situation: there was political and economic stability and the UK had confidence in the health sector and the wider development context. The UK appreciated that the Government of Ghana proactively reached out and shaped new relationships with DPs. Ghana was 'ahead of the pack' in adopting these relationships and the UK demonstrated confidence through its sizeable increased funding.

Phase Four (2007-2012): The height of the SWAp and DFID's financial support - but doubts start to creep in

Core UK Programme: Health Sector Support Programme I (HSSP-I), 2008-2012

Value of Programme: ca £41.2 million

The SWAp expands and monitoring tools are refined, but many DPs felt results were disappointing.

Ghana's health sector

The 2007 National Health Policy: Creating Wealth through Health guided the development of the Programme of Work 2007-2011 (POW-III). This was truncated in 2010 and replaced with the first 4-year Health Sector Medium Term Development Plan 2010-2013 (HSMTDP-I)³. HSMTDP-I adopted Universal Health Coverage (UHC), which remained at the centre of successive HSMTDPs.

These broad plans were supported by technical policies that guided the development of annual workplans at all levels. A notable SWAp feature was the Holistic Assessment Tool – see Annex 1. This Ghana-specific tool was an important part of joint working arrangements, critical to the monitoring and planning of annual plans.

Health improvements largely stalled and it became clear that achievement of MDGs 4 and 5 was unlikely⁴. Some DPs began to express concerns over organisational challenges that they had hoped the SWAp would tackle, notably tensions between the MoH and the Ghana Health Service. Moreover there was a resurgence in support from some DPs for highly vertical programmes which went against the reforms that had strengthened Regional and District Health Management Teams in the 1990s.

DFID in Ghana

HSSP-I aimed to accelerate progress towards the health MDGs. DFID continued with its strong support for SWAp principles. It did so through its policy engagement and reviews of performance that were nominally linked to the following year's funding

³ This was to align with the National Development Planning Commission's new four-year planning cycle.

⁴ MDG 4: Reduce the Under-5 mortality by two thirds. MDG 5: Reduce maternal mortality by three quarters. (1990-2015)

– as was Ghana’s performance against macro policy areas (financial management, pro-poor policies, and human rights).

DFID’s overall investment continued to grow in Ghana, matching an increase in its global spend on health (Lowcock & Dissanayake, 2024). DFID health spend reached its zenith with SBS (ca £40 million), TA (around £2.5 million) and about £34 million reaching the health sector through GBS.

UK international development policy

In 2010, the new Conservative Government retained the 0.7% commitment and swiftly moved to emphasise evidence, value for money and accountability.

Gradually from 2009 the aid effectiveness agenda was under challenge – the UK economy slumped after the 2007 global financial crash and public support for aid appeared to decline. The perspective shifted from viewing results as a ‘contribution’ to national outcomes to emphasising ‘attribution’ – a direct link between UK inputs and country level outcomes. Management processes were reorganised around attributable results. The use of logframes (the main tool for accountability and reporting) meant pre-planned targets, rather than monitoring based around the looser notion of contribution to outcomes. DFID headquarters set targets and country offices bid for funds based on what they said they could contribute to these targets. The understanding and use of the term ‘results’ changed. As Valters and Whitty state: *“Used colloquially, ‘results’ simply means developmental aims or ends. Yet the results agenda has come to represent a political agenda for foreign aid, associated with fixed target-setting, which has changed the way DFID operates around the world”* (Valters & Whitty, 1997).

These policy shifts were quickly adopted in Ghana, where there was a degree of disappointment in the pace and nature of change delivered by the SWAp. During HSSP-I, the language of DFID programme documents became much more about health outcomes and in particular ones the MoH could control, such as skilled birth attendance. Less consideration was given to health outcomes that required inputs from beyond the MoH. One example of this was water quality, even though the SWAp partnership had fostered cross-Ministerial engagement on this. A consequence of this sharper results focus was a loss of emphasis on strengthening health systems. There was greater focus on logframes which required more defined and pre-determined results. In Ghana, the DFID health logframe still used national results frameworks and SWAp management arrangements, whilst also responding to DFID’s growing reporting requirements. The value for money agenda also demanded greater fiduciary scrutiny.

Phase Five (2013-2019): The demise of the SWAp

Core UK Programme: Health System Support Programme II (HSSP-II), 2013-2018

Value of Programme: ca £59.1 million

Health improvements largely stall, Ghana/DP relations deteriorate and the SWAp ends, being replaced by earmarked FA and projects.

Ghana's health sector

Ghana's Health Sector Medium Term Development Plan II 2014-2017 (HSMTDP-II) sustained Ghana's UHC commitment. It noted that whilst there had been improvements in many areas, quality and equity remained significant issues. There was a review and re-prioritisation of the CHPS in 2015.

Financing challenges continued. A major concern was escalating costs, with 90% of the MoH budget going to wages. Domestic health spending stalled amidst ongoing national macro-economic pressures. No progress was made towards sustainability of national health insurance, as scale-up of the capitation payment system was abandoned with the change of government in 2017.

In July 2011 Ghana moved from low-income to lower-middle-income country (LMIC) status, according to World Bank classifications. The new classification resulted from a re-basement of national income data, rather than a substantive change in Ghana's economic circumstances. Nevertheless, middle-income status meant higher expectations on domestic resource generation for public spending and standards of governance and management. Because Ghana's move to LMIC status was sudden, DPs took time to respond, particularly as there was a general feeling that reclassification was based on a statistical, rather than real economic, change.

DFID in Ghana

The Health Sector Support Programme II 2013-2018 (HSSP-II) supported the Medium- Term Development Plan with budget support until 2015. The design of HSSP-II reflected the recognition that improvements in health had slowed since 2008. DFID held that the sector's problems required a stronger focus on governance and should include support for regulatory bodies, as well as a sustained focus on equity.

The primary modality, SBS, was retained until 2014. However, in a departure from earlier programmes, there was also earmarked FA to three authorities – the National Health Insurance Authority, the Food and Drugs Authority and the Mental Health Authority - with funding released on completion of agreed reform-orientated annual plans.

The HSSP-II logframe reflected DFID's evolving policy on results. It started by adopting national targets, was amended a number of times and ended with DFID-specific quantifiable deliverables – reflecting DFID's general shift to 'what does our money deliver?' with less concern for 'what does our policy engagement deliver?'. These changes resulted in HSSP-II employing consultants to provide additional management and fiduciary oversight.

In 2015 DFID shifted its financial support from SBS to earmarked FA. There were concerns about stagnating health sector performance, sector governance, leadership, acceptable fiduciary risk levels and financing decisions, but also a growing view that neither General nor Sector Budget Support could incentivise improvements (DFID, 2019). This was, in effect, the end of the SWAp era.

DFID followed the World Bank by providing earmarked support to CHPS. The World Bank was becoming an increasingly dominant partner in the health sector; its analyses of the sector's performance and how to accelerate improvements were influential within DFID. The Bank started providing earmarked FA for six regions - DFID mirrored this model in the remaining 4 regions. As an LMIC, Ghana arguably ought to have funded primary health care itself. However, the World Bank and DFID agreed to provide time-bound support in response to a Presidential commitment to accelerate primary care through CHPS and improved governance and accountability. This helped deal with DFID's desire to reduce its exposure to risk, as well as the feeling that the transition to LMIC had happened too quickly.

The Multi-Donor Budget Support partnership, which provided GBS, started to break down when Ghana's Government and the DPs could not come to consensus on the Performance Assessment Framework during the 2013 review. There were concerns about the macro-economy in terms of the use of the windfall revenue from oil: over-spending, inflation and currency problems led to Ghana's request to the IMF for an extended credit facility in 2015 (DFID, 2014). Alleged mismanagement of public procurement in the health sector and a bloated wage bill underscored DPs' waning confidence in the Government's commitment to public sector management and poverty reduction. The result was the end of GBS in 2015.

It is difficult to tease out the cause and effect of the changes to aid instruments. The UK's attitudes to risk in international development, value for money and modalities such as budget support were changing significantly in the mid-2010s under the Conservative government. There were also reasons to have doubts about Ghana's management of resources and decreased confidence that DPs' engagement was sufficiently effective in advancing reform. A suspicious fire at Central Medical Stores in 2015 further stoked feelings amongst DPs that there were problems with the management of development funds. The UK High Commissioner stated "*The UK Parliament is worried about the Central Medical Stores arson*" (Offin-Amaniampong, 2017).

Two indices related to corruption also suggest challenges in Ghana during the mid-2010s. Transparency International's Corruption Perception Index recorded a fairly stable situation in Ghana from 2012-2015, but then a larger-than-usual (but still modest) drop between 2015 and 2016 (Transparency International, 2025). The World Bank's public sector transparency, accountability and corruption rating also showed a worsening situation between 2013 and 2016 (World Bank, 2025).

During this phase DFID established a new instrument for technical assistance: a TA Fund managed by the MoH, rather than DFID. This was to fund policy work and was primarily used for financial management strengthening, health financing reforms and workforce planning. At the time the Fund was criticised for being used too often for

activities which were not a priority for DFID – for example activities in the largest hospital in the country. Management arrangements tightened over time, with disagreements about the transparency of spending.

In retrospect, the list of important policy areas that were addressed through the TA Fund is impressive, including:

- development of the National Health Policy
- burden of disease study
- health financing strategy, including transition from external finance
- standard treatment guidelines
- legal instruments to regulate professionals
- workforce planning model.

Moreover, this was not expensive, costing less than £5 million of the £59 million health programme.

The Independent Commission for Aid Impact (ICAI) report

ICAI, the Independent Commission for Aid Impact, published a review of UK support to Ghana from 2011 to 2019 (ICAI, 2020). It criticised decisions about where to cut expenditure that were not based on sufficiently robust analysis of the consequences for service delivery and outcomes. The social sectors accounted for 84% of DFID Ghana's reduction in bilateral spending during 2011-2019, when both poverty and geographic inequalities were worsening. As a result, development gains achieved through these programmes were at risk of being reversed. ICAI recommended that transitions towards ending bilateral funding should include consideration of whether the gap left would be filled, and to work at an appropriate pace to reflect that. ICAI stressed that this recommendation was not against the reduction of bilateral budgets in transition countries – it was about the way and pace in which this was done

The health portfolio was reviewed very positively as having had a strong focus on vulnerable people and people in poverty. The review assessed the effectiveness of HSSP-II in improving access to primary health care, concluding:

“UK aid’s contribution to improved community health services has been significant..... Without its support the expansion of facilities and the delivery of the maternal and child health programme at facilities would not have occurred to the same degree. While outcome results are mixed, the general trend is that more services were made available closer to communities in the four DFID regions as a result of UK aid support. We therefore find that UK aid made a strong contribution to medium results” (Elsy et al., 2023).

UK international development policy

In 2015 the UK legislated that 0.7% of gross national income should be spent on aid – it became a statutory duty. International development policy kept evolving: the role of the private sector increased and there was a growing emphasis on how development assistance could contribute to furthering the UK's interests.

The results agenda moved towards short-term, narrow results of projects, and away from wider processes of change. Predictions of outcomes (despite often operating in volatile environments) and assurances of accountability to the UK taxpayer became increasingly important.

The move from 'shared' national results to 'attributable' results accelerated. After years of accepting shared results of a multi-stakeholder partnership, DFID demanded UK-specific results. The focus on accountability in terms of evidenced impact is entirely appropriate, but by its very nature the impact of spending in other countries cannot be isolated in terms of just the UK spend. Over time DFID worked out practical project management arrangements that allowed some flexibility.

This interest in attributable results and low risk tolerance led the UK to question the effectiveness of SWAs and FA. DFID Ghana gradually changed its portfolio by increasing its focus on the performance of Global Health Initiatives and UK-managed programmes.

Phase Six (2019-2023): Ghana beyond aid, COVID and an unstable period in UK development assistance

Core UK Programme: Leave No-one Behind (LNOB), 2019-2024
Partnerships Beyond Aid (PBA), 2020-2025

Value of programme: LNOB initially budgeted £39m; expenditure £27.4 million
PBA initially budgeted £25 million; expenditure £14.6 million

A very different FCDO portfolio, with frequent cuts to budgets, relatively little FA and social sector, rather than health-specific, programmes.

Ghana's Beyond Aid

In May 2019, the Government of Ghana issued Ghana Beyond Aid (GBA), a national agenda for economic transformation which was intended to bring about a shift in mindset and behaviour. GBA described a move away from aid towards self-reliance based on the private sector. However, it made clear that it was not a rejection of aid, but rather a realignment of engagement with DPs to ensure that future aid supported economic transformation. It set a target to increase Ghana's own contribution to basic public services with a reducing reliance on external grants. Aid should be "*redirected to areas where they are likely to have more catalytic effects*" (Government of The Republic of Ghana, 2019).

GBA's economic growth targets required annual GDP growth of 9.5%. However, in reality Ghana experienced low growth (0.5% in 2020, 3.1% in 2022 and 1.5% in 2023) and high inflation, peaking at 54% in December 2022. The internationally defined poverty rate (\$2.15 in 2017 USD PPP) increased to 32.6% in 2023, from 25.2% in 2017. Unemployment and food insecurity worsened, in part due to COVID (World Bank, 2023a). Geographical, income and social inequities worsened, with the impacts of the pandemic falling disproportionately on women and in the north of the country (World Bank, 2023b).

Ghana's health sector

Health spending as a proportion of Government expenditure reached 8.1% in 2019, but fell to 6.7% in 2023. (The Abuja Declaration recommends 15%). Despite the sentiments behind Ghana Beyond Aid, the Government was clear that it wanted increased FA from the UK and other DPs, to help protect the social sectors from the economic crisis.

The Health Sector Medium Term Development Plan IV 2022-2025 (HSMTDP-IV) focused on UHC, with a strong emphasis on health systems strengthening. The focus on systems was a response to the fact that the overall sector performance score (based on the Holistic Assessment Tool) had declined from 3.6 (out of 5) for 2019 to 2.6 for 2021.

Phase 6 included the COVID-19 pandemic. A WHO study concluded that Ghana's response to COVID-19 was reasonably successful, with a Case Fatality Rate of 0.9%, lower than the rates in Nigeria, Kenya and Burkina Faso (Agongo et al., 2023; John Hopkins, 2025).

FCDO in Ghana

The Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO) was created in 2020 with the merger of the Foreign and Commonwealth Office and DFID; they had been separate ministries for 23 years.

FCDO support in Phase 6 was very different to previous phases. There were two major social sector programmes, rather than health-specific ones. This widened scope brought challenges (it was more complicated than just an arrangement with the MoH) and in practice it proved difficult to develop integrated services.

Programme budgets were lower, cut over time, and subject to annual re-negotiation. Spending on the social sector was about 45% of UK bilateral spend in Ghana in 2019, whereas it had been around 70% in the early 2010s (ICAI, 2020). The percentage of the budget spent as FA was lower, with more emphasis on non-governmental partners. The problem of budget cuts was so severe that the 2023 Annual Review for one programme stated that FCDO budget uncertainty delayed implementation and "*undermined FCDO's credibility*" (FCDO, 2023c). The focus moved away from direct support for service delivery (with the exception of mental health) to systems strengthening, including in relation to demand for health care and accountability.

A variety of aid modalities were used in the two programmes – World Bank Trust Funds; commercial contracts; funding for WHO and UNICEF; a contract to an umbrella body to provide funding for smaller CSOs; and an FCDO-managed Synergy Fund, which included up to £2 million of results-based FA to the MoH for milestones related to mental health. Between the two programmes there were contracts with some 15 different partners.

Alongside Canada, Gavi and the Global Financing Facility for Women, Children and Adolescents, FCDO contributed to the World Bank Primary Health Care Investment Programme. This Programme was the closest that the health sector in Phase 6

came to a SWAp. Whilst the dominant role of the World Bank distinguished it from a SWAp, it had some similarities – government/DP dialogue about sectoral issues, a pooled fund, jointly agreed targets, and use of government financing and monitoring systems. A major advantage to FCDO was that its contribution gave it a “seat at the table” for dialogue with the MoH.

Another feature of UK support during Phase 6 was an increased focus on “cross-government” involvement in international development and on Ghana-UK partnerships. This trend, together with the contractually fragmented nature of the two social sector programmes, marked an end to the focus on streamlined support to the health sector, with the relationship between the MoH and FCDO at its core.

UK international development policy

The period 2019-2023 was an unusually volatile time for UK international development. A number of global crises required emergency responses, including COVID-19, Afghanistan and Ukraine. Ministers and government priorities changed frequently – there were four Prime Ministers and five Foreign Secretaries between 2019 and 2023. In 2021 the government announced that, due to the economic impact of COVID, it would “temporarily” spend 0.5% of GNI on aid, thus putting on hold its statutory duty to spend 0.7%⁵. The development programme’s budget endured periods of uncertainty and significant cuts.

In 2023, two UK government publications articulated the changes in international development thinking that had become apparent since the recent budget cuts. The White Paper, *International Development in a Contested World: Ending Extreme Poverty and Tackling Climate Change* (FCDO, 2023b), focused on poverty reduction. There was an emphasis on long-term, equitable partnerships (“*beyond an outdated ‘donor-recipient’ model*”) and the key role of UK expertise, including in universities and the NHS.

In practice, this approach led to much more fragmented UK support – there was less money being spent, spread across more partnerships and projects. Moreover, the focus on UK partners meant that an increasing proportion of the budget went to UK institutions. ICAI noted that this “*appeared contrary to the UK’s commitment to untying all its development aid*” (ICAI, 2023).

The FCDO’s May 2023 Global Health Framework reflected the same themes of poverty, partnerships and UK expertise (FCDO, 2023a). It highlighted the importance of global health security, UHC and health systems strengthening. As with the White Paper there was a focus on working through partnerships (with other governments, civil society, academia, the private sector and other UK government departments).

The Ghana programme reflected the White Paper and the Global Health Framework well. There were many partnerships that included a UK partner, and support for the efficiency of the health sector.

⁵ In 2025, the Government announced that UK aid spending would be “gradually reduced” from 0.5% of GNI to 0.3% in 2027. House of Commons Library (2025) UK aid: Reducing spending to 0.3% of GNI by 2027/28.

Discussion and policy implications

Aid Effectiveness

'Aid effectiveness' came to the fore in the early 2000s, as it was increasingly recognised that development assistance should produce better impacts. The 2005 Paris Declaration, which was endorsed by more than 100 countries and agencies including Ghana and the UK, identified five central pillars of effective aid - ownership, alignment, harmonisation, managing for results and mutual accountability. The crux of the Declaration was the importance of respecting a country's priorities and systems, and for DPs to avoid creating parallel plans and systems for financial flows and reporting. The aid effectiveness agenda waned over the 2010s; in the early 2020s, however, there was renewed interest in how to operationalise its principles.

This paper demonstrates how this macro picture played out in Ghana. It has described changes to UK development policy over time and how the policies sometimes chimed with thinking in Ghana, and at other times clashed. In the late 1990s both Ghana and the UK were interested in finding ways to operationalise closer, more equal and efficient partnerships. By 2010 the UK was demanding information on attributed results whilst Ghana wanted joint monitoring and continued use of the Holistic Assessment Tool. In the 2020s the UK largely funded stand-alone projects and promoted roles for British partners. However, FCDO still saw the value in contributing to a multi-donor fund (the World Bank PHC Investment Program) in order to secure a seat at policy dialogues.

A variety of aid instruments were used during the 30 years, ranging from stand-alone projects to GBS. The SWAp lasted from about 1998 to 2015, a considerable amount of time. Interest in the principles underpinning a SWAp – alignment with government priorities, shared finance and monitoring systems, joint planning to avoid duplication and gaps – are enduring, whether or not a SWAp is the precise approach or the term being used. For this reason, historic lessons about Ghana's SWAp are relevant today – what has been learnt in terms of aid effectiveness?

Many of the principles of aid effectiveness were realised during the heyday of the SWAp (ca 1998-2012, broadly Phases 2-4). There was a systematic process for planning, implementing, and monitoring activities, which some but not all DPs adhered to. Maintaining this arrangement was hard work for all concerned, in terms of both mutual trust and practical logistics. There were definite advantages in terms of coherence and strengthening Government systems - the current format of Ghana's Health Sector Medium Term Development Plans, with their review of previous performance and clear priorities, is a legacy of the systematic, evidence-oriented approach of the SWAp. There was the opportunity to discuss some important policy challenges, but there were areas of the SWAp where DPs had less leverage, for example contracting out work to non-state providers (the Government of Ghana was reluctant to pay other providers with 'its' money) and developing accountability to Ghanaians (accountability programmes generally have to be funded separately). There were also no magic bullets to long-standing problems such as health inequalities.

Maintaining the relationships was about political will, committed leadership and robust management. It is maybe inevitable that SWAPs are time-limited, as the mutual satisfaction with arrangements is very difficult to maintain over a long period.

A good deal has been written about health SWAPs, including Ghana's (Peters et al., 2013; Vaillancourt, 2009; Walford, 2007a). The general conclusion of these papers was that SWAPs had clear advantages on paper, but that in practice it could be difficult to get common arrangements to work well. A six-country review concluded: "There is strong consensus among countries and DPs that more rational and country-led management of aid is a goal worth pursuing. But the adoption of a SWAP does not automatically lead to improved development effectiveness.". The review then identified four critical success factors for a SWAP to have a positive effect on health outcomes:

- Programmes of Work with ambitious-but-feasible targets and relevant reforms;
- strong national capacity and systems to implement common management arrangements;
- partnerships with appropriate membership, clear roles, and the ability to work together constructively;
- predictable flow and use of resources, both domestic and external.

The Ghana experience demonstrates these critical success factors. Over time, however, DPs (including FCDO) became disillusioned with progress towards targets and there were issues related to the predictability and management of both Ghanaian and international funds. DPs, in part influenced by their domestic aid policies, judged that macro-economic mismanagement harmed the health sector.

Learning from the Ghana/UK experience

Aid Instruments

1. Different aid instruments serve different purposes.

Financial Aid can be appropriate for sharing the risk of tackling long-term knotty challenges, such as developing an efficient national health insurance scheme. This allows finite domestic resources to focus on providing essential services.

Sector Budget Support enables an appreciation of, and engagement in, the whole sector (including resource trade-offs) and is the most effective way to achieve strategic policy influence by DPs (e.g. about equity). **Projects** can be useful to tackle new issues or to develop new ways of working; they can be managed to be as compatible as possible with government plans and implementation systems.

2. Technical Assistance (TA) planning and management arrangements should be well embedded in government systems and respond to government requests.

SWAps

3. A SWAp can include several aid instruments so long as they all advance the principles of the SWAp concept: '**one plan, one budget, one report**'.

4. It is difficult to maintain a SWAp over a long period of time, not least because what constitutes 'good enough' governance and the rate of progress towards outcomes are subjective judgements that can change over time.

5. Ideally SWAps should address non-health sector policies and programmes that impact on public health, such as water quality. Ghana's SWAp had ambitions for this, but in practice made limited inroads.

Planning and results

6. Indicators of results should cover some policy and systems outputs, some service outcomes and some health impacts. The logframe/'theory of change' needs to be kept up to date. Systems strengthening takes time: it is important to have realistic targets and sustained commitment and to be willing to adapt based on evidence and changing contexts.

7. Five-year sector plans are essential, but often aspirational. **The quality of annual plans is imperative.** Annual plans are often overlooked but they are a crucial part of negotiations in a SWAp.

8. 'Keep it real' by ensuring a focus on district and sub-district level delivery and adequate application of equity to policies and indicators.

9. It is important that a focus on process and risks (e.g. fiduciary risks) does not distract from a **focus on results**.

Politics and influence

10. Convening power and influence with the MoH and in the DP community are achieved through sustained high quality technical and political engagement.

11. Domestic politics influence DPs' decision-making in country, often heading in different directions from local agendas.

The importance – and challenges - of monitoring results is a consistent theme over the 30 years.

From a situation in the 1990s where systems and processes were given as much attention as outcomes, the focus on measurable outcomes gradually sharpened. Around 2000 (Phase 2) it became clear that improvements in service delivery and health outcomes were painfully slow, and not reliably measured. During Phase 3, information was used systematically to try to address persistent challenges, including inequalities. By Phase 4 (2007-2012) the Common Management Arrangements had broken down, meaning that Ghanaian officials were being asked for increasing technical and managerial information by DPs behaving increasingly unilaterally. This was the era of projects and attributable targets. DFID in particular wanted more information on outputs linked directly to DFID spending and targets.

The Independent Commission for Aid Impact identified an unintended consequence of an extreme focus on results, targets and attribution – it led to more direct contracting with non-state providers for quicker results. This was not necessarily because the non-state provider was the most appropriate (though it sometimes was), but because this was a quicker, easier way of operating.

A focus on outcomes is obviously appropriate, and can lead to well-targeted, incentivised work. By their very nature, however, DPs' outcomes will always be shared with in-country partners. Good outcome identification, monitoring and reporting take time and skills, and the more partners which share the same targets the better. The more streamlined the monitoring requirements, the more possible it is to implement coordinated plans. The Holistic Assessment Tool remains a useful product of the SWAp era, though there were gaps in its use and issues about quality.

It would be satisfying to conclude with a statement about the extent to which DFID/FCDO contributed to health in Ghana. In 1993, the infant mortality rate was 69/1,000 and life expectancy at birth was 56 years. By 2023, infant mortality had more than halved (28/1,000) and 9 years was added to life expectancy. During that period the UK contributed more than £230 million to the health sector and the UK's technical support was broadly judged to be relevant, well designed and delivered. Given the scale and relevance to the UK's support over 30 years of health gain, it is reasonable to assert the UK has had a positive impact on health in Ghana⁶.

Despite, the more recent compromised provision of predictable assistance which impacted on the UK's reputation as an accountable partner, the Ghana/UK co-operation is a story of remarkable strength.

⁶ Lowcock and Dissanayake concluded that UK development spending had had a positive impact on health in 18 focus countries, including Ghana (Lowcock & Dissanayake, 2024).

References

- Addai, E., & Gaere, L. (2001). Capacity Building and Systems Development for Sector Wide Approaches (SWAs): The Experience of the Ghana Health Sector. In *DFID & Ghana MoH (Unpublished)*.
- Agongo, E., Delanyo, D., Anaseba, D., Adongo, E. A., Acheampong, F. I., & Awekeya, H. (2023). *Ghana: a primary health care case study in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic*. World Health Organization. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/372716/9789240073012-eng.pdf>
- Asamoah-Baah, A., & Smithson, P. (1999). Donors and the Ministry of Health: new partnerships in Ghana. *World Health Organisation*. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/66156>
- Cassels, A. (1997). *A guide to sector-wide approaches for health development: concepts, issues and working arrangements*. https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/63811/WHO_ARA_97.12.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- DFID. (2014). *General Budget Support Ghana 2012-2015: 2013 Annual review*.
- DFID. (2019). *HSSP II Project Completion Report*.
- Elsay, H., Abboah-Offei, M., Vidyasagaran, A. L., Anaseba, D., Wallace, L., Nwameme, A., Gyasi, A., Ayim, A., Ansah-Ofei, A., Amedzro, N., Dovlo, D., Agongo, E., Awoonor-Williams, K., & Agyepong, I. (2023). Implementation of the Community-based Health Planning and Services (CHPS) in rural and urban Ghana: a history and systematic review of what works, for whom and why. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1105495>
- EU Commission, World Bank IEG, Government of Ghana, Government of Denmark, Government of France, & Government of Germany. (2017). *Joint evaluation of budget support to Ghana (2005-2015): High-level summary*. https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-06/evaluation-ghana-bs-summary_en.pdf
- FCDO. (2023a). *Global Health Framework: working together towards a healthier world*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/global-health-framework-working-together-towards-a-healthier-world>
- FCDO. (2023b). *International development in a contested world: ending extreme poverty and tackling climate change, a white paper on international development*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/international-development-in-a-contested-world-ending-extreme-poverty-and-tackling-climate-change>

- FCDO. (2023c). *Partnerships Beyond Aid: Annual Review 2022-23*.
- Ghana MoH. (1996). *Common Management Arrangements*.
- Ghana MoH. (1997). The Health of the Nation Reflections on the First Five Year Health Sector Programme of Work. In *Government of Ghana*.
<https://moh.gov.gh/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/5yr-POW-1997-2001.pdf>
- Government of The Republic of Ghana. (2019). *Ghana Beyond Aid Charter and Strategy Document*. https://dohaembassy.gov.gh/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Ghana-Beyond-Aid-Charter-and-Strategy-Documents-April-2019_Agricinghana-Media-Copy.pdf
- ICAI. (2020). *The changing nature of UK aid in Ghana*.
<https://icai.independent.gov.uk/review/ghana/>
- ICAI. (2023). *UK aid under pressure: a synthesis of ICAI findings from 2019 to 2023*. <https://icai.independent.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/UK-aid-under-pressure-synthesis-of-ICAI-findings-2019-23.pdf>
- John Hopkins. (2025). *COVID-19 Mortality Analysis*. John Hopkins Coronavirus Resource Centre. <https://coronavirus.jhu.edu/data/mortality>
- Lawson, A., Boadi, G., Gharthey, A., Gharthey, A., Killick, T., Agha, Z., & Williamson, T. (2007). *Volume One: Evaluation Results and Recommendations on Future Design & Management of Ghana MDDBS*.
<https://media.odi.org/documents/247.pdf>
- Lowcock, M., & Dissanayake, R. (2024). *The Rise and Fall of the Department for International Development*. Center for Global Development.
<https://www.cgdev.org/publication/rise-and-fall-department-international-development>
- Offin-Amaniampong, G. (2017). *The Anatomy Of GHANA Medical Stores Fire: What Did We Learn From It?* Modern Ghana.
<https://www.modernghana.com/news/791958/the-anatomy-of-ghana-medical-stores-fire-what-did-we-learn.html>
- Peters, D. H., Paina, L., & Schleimann, F. (2013). Sector-wide approaches (SWAps) in health: what have we learned? *Health Policy and Planning*, 28(8), 884–890. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czs128>
- Transparency International. (2025). *Corruption Perceptions Index 2024: Score timeseries since 2012*. Transparency International.
<https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2024/index/gha>
- Vaillancourt, D. A. (2009). *Do health sector-wide approaches achieve results?*
<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/178491468155377271/do-health-sector-wide-approaches-achieve-results>

- Valters, C., & Whitty, B. (1997). *The politics of the results agenda in DFID 1997-2017*. <https://media.odi.org/documents/11730.pdf>
- Waddington, C., & Enyimayew, K. A. (1989). A price to pay: The impact of user charges in ashanti-akim district, Ghana. *The International Journal of Health Planning and Management*, 4(1), 17–47. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hpm.4740040104>
- Waddington, C., & Enyimayew, K. A. (1990). A price to pay, part 2: The impact of user charges in the Volta region of Ghana. *The International Journal of Health Planning and Management*, 5(4), 287–312. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hpm.4740050405>
- Walford, V. (1998). *Developing Sector Wide Approaches in the Health Sector: An Issues Paper for DFID Advisers and Field Managers*. <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/57a08da6ed915d3cfd001b44/Developing-Sector-Wide-Approaches-in-the-Health-Sector.pdf>
- Walford, V. (2007a). *A Review of SWAps in Africa*.
- Walford, V. (2007b). *Evaluation of the Netherlands-DFID Partnership in the health sector in Ghana*.
- World Bank. (2023a). *Ghana - First Resilient Recovery Development Policy Financing*. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/099122123140098673>
- World Bank. (2023b). *Ghana - Tree Crop Diversification Project*. <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/099060523170036076/bosib038a04de90e80bd7f0b810d83983a4>
- World Bank. (2025). *World Bank Country Policy and Institutional Assessments indicators*. Indicators. <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?dsid=31&series=IQ.CPA.FIN.Q.XQ>